

Original Research Report

Coping Strategies Adopted by Families during COVID-19 Pandemic Lockdown in Nsukka Urban Area, Nigeria

Ifeanyi E. Omeje^{1*} Chiamaka A. Chukwuone¹

¹Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, University of Nigeria, 41001 Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria

***Correspondence:** Ifeanyi E. Omeje, Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, University of Nigeria, 41001 Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria (Email: edithomeje00@gmail.com)

Abstract: This study investigates the coping strategies adopted by families during COVID-19 pandemic lockdown in Nsukka urban of Enugu state, Nigeria. The design adopted in this study was descriptive survey design. The study was carried out in Nsukka Urban of Enugu state, which covered three communities (Nkpunano, Nru and Ihe-Owerre). Population of study comprised of 417,700 families from the three communities in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu state. A sample size of 399 families (133 from each of the three communities) was drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique with the aid of Taro Yamane's formula. The study findings indicate that families in Nsukka urban were into making of local nose mask during the COVID-19 lockdown ($\bar{x} = 3.94$, $SD = 1.26$). The study further revealed that families were also using money from saved family income as a means of survival during this period ($\bar{x} = 3.94$, $SD = 1.26$). the findings also shows that the families most observed safety measure during COVID-19 lockdown is regular washing of hands with soap and water and cleaning of hands with hand sanitizer; they also cover their nose with mask ($\bar{x} = 3.94$, $SD = 1.26$). This study will help enlighten families, states and the country at large on ways people adopt in order to acquire skills, save money for unforeseen circumstances, and also adhere to COVID-19 safety measures such as washing hands regularly with soap and water, cleaning hands with hand sanitizer and also cover their nose with face masks.

Keywords: Coping Strategies, COVID-19, Families, Nigeria, Pandemics

1. Introduction

The present millennium has witnessed a series of health challenges ranging from the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome, first discovered in Saudi Arabia in 2012, the Western African Ebola virus in Guinea between 2013 and 2016, to the Brazilian Zika virus in 2015. Unexpectedly, the beginning of the year 2020 saw the emergence of yet another deadly virus (COVID-19), which is a severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) (World Health Organization-WHO, 2020). The first index case of COVID-19 surfaced as unknown acute pneumonia in Wuhan hospital, a city in Eastern China. Consequently, WHO declared the virus a global pandemic on March 11, 2020 and having been previously recognized as a “Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC)” on January 30, 2020 (Cai et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020). The outbreak of the virus in China and its spread to other countries including Nigeria has had a destructive impact on health, economy, infrastructure, human existence and food. However, the evidence in recent studies and literature showed that more researchers, governments and major stakeholders have rather engaged in research that intends to bring a cure to the virus (Amusan & Agunyai, 2021). However, other studies have investigated the pandemic’s impact on violence against children and women (Peterman et al., 2020), health (Berge et al., 2020), economy (Piguillem & Shi, 2020), education (United Nations Coordinated Appeal, 2020) and human safety (Lattouf, 2020). This has created some gaps in exposing the coping strategies adopted by families, which could help in the future tackling of this type of pandemic outbreak.

Pandemics are global or worldwide epidemics occurring over a wide area, spreading across international boundaries and affecting a large number of people (Kelly, 2011). It can also be seen as a simultaneous global transmission of diseases or viruses that cut across boundaries and continents. It is population immunity, virology or disease severity (Kelly, 2011). It is a disease outbreak that spreads across the world. Its rate of spread and infection is simultaneous and almost the same across countries of the world. From this definition, it is obvious that the COVID-19 disease is a pandemic, as it has all the conditions or features of a pandemic (Amusan & Agunyai, 2021). The pandemic since its outbreak, had severely threatened human existence. It is a virus that knows no border or person, nor does it discriminate based on nationality. It affects all humans, countries and economies – a confirmation of ‘globalization and its discontents’ (Stiglitz, 2002). On February 27th, 2020, Nigeria reported its first case of the COVID-19 disease, and by the third week of March, the total number of cases had risen to 22 across Nigeria (Ehanire, 2020). While the number of cases in Nigeria at the time paled in comparison to other countries, it was clear that the ravaging effects of the virus in other countries made it a threat to Nigeria’s fragile health system. In response to this, the government took drastic measures to try to curb the spread of the virus in the country, by instituting a four-week lockdown and halting all non-essential activity in four of the most industrialized states in the country - Lagos, Ogun, and Kano, and Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (Obiakor et al., 2021). Conceptually speaking, lockdown has been referred to as an emergency response imposed by the government, mandating people to stay indoors in the event of an outbreak (Ajide et al., 2020). In other words, Amusan and Agunyai (2021) explained lockdown as a policy or an order adopted by governments in different nations to limit the spread of the virus. It is an order that outlawed people from moving out of their homes. It specifically states that, every household remains in-door or at

home for safety to prevent contact with persons with the virus. In the case of COVID-19, the ultimate goal of a lockdown measure is to flatten the curve of the novel virus. The exercise entails the closure of all activities-based centres such as schools, hotels, clubs, and religious houses that could make a sizable number of people come together. This apart, directives such as social distancing, banning of congregation of more 20 people, and compulsory usage of the face masks, particularly, in public places were all forcefully enforced (CDC, 2020; NCDC, 2020; WHO, 2020). According to Ajide et al. (2020), Figure 1 shows the distribution of COVID-19 cases in Nigeria states presenting confirmed, active, recovered and death of COVID-19 patients.

Lockdown is interchangeably used for quarantine but the two concepts are not the same, although they serve the same purpose of limiting the spread of the virus. While quarantine is aimed at persons who have come in contact with people who have tested positive for COVID-19 or persons who have travelled to or returned from places with a high incidence of COVID-19 (Ajide et al., 2020; Amusan & Agunyai, 2021). Someshwar et al. (2020) similarly shared the view that quarantine is aimed at separation and isolation of individuals who have been in close contact with a positively tested patient. Lockdown is a measure that closes the entire country except essential services such as healthcare service, pharmaceutical service and security services, amongst others. COVID-19 may be producing a stressful environment for parents and families in several ways: Parents may worry about the economic and physical health of their family; they may be concerned about their children's social isolation from peers and teachers; they may be preoccupied with the management, duration, and outcomes of homeschooling; they may have doubts about their ability to provide information to their children about COVID-19 in a reassuring and age-appropriate manner; and they may mistrust the government's intention to provide support for parents juggling childcare, home-based working, and/or summer holidays (Fontanesi et al., 2020). However, the life condition of families suddenly and deeply changed. In the home environment, the educational role of parents for children has become even much crucial than before. Children have only their parents around them, to provide support with homework when necessary and promote a positive development and new learning experiences for toddlers and preschoolers (Wang et al., 2020). Parents have been left alone not only in taking care of home schooling their children, but also in general in the management of their children and of the home environment. All other educational services are closed, babysitters and grandparents are not available, and contact with peers is not allowed (Spinelli et al., 2020). Many parents also must do smart-working and handling time and spaces to work with children around may be very problematic. This situation has significantly increased the risk of experiencing stress and negative emotions in parents, with a potentially cascading effect on children's wellbeing (Sprang & Silman, 2013).

Hence, despite its positive effect in reducing the number of new infected cases, the mobility restriction and social isolation as associated with quarantine are major concerns for families' psychological wellbeing. Related to this, the health care situation of the country is fragile, calling for attention with overcrowding and increase in death patients (Spinelli et al., 2020). It is becoming very common to know at least one person who tested positive to COVID-19 or was hospitalized, and, most regretfully, to have experienced the loss of a person due to COVID-19. This might generate fear and preoccupation in parents and children,

even for families who do not have to face health problems (Liu et al., 2020). Available evidence shows that lockdown has led to psychological disturbances, ranging from suicides to depression, which has led to broken marriages and homes and stress disorders (Someshwar et al., 2020). Buttressing the negative effects of the lockdown, Oke (2020) noted that locking down people in the Nigerian case is like pushing them into hunger and pangs of hunger will lead to anger. Specifically, it has led to protests at the community level and intra-household violence against women and children. This is because the lockdown order was haphazardly copied and announced for implementation without a comprehensive plan for palliatives in Nigeria. Thus, the COVID-19 pandemic, which has necessitated the lockdown order, has not only pushed people into hunger, but also made them, especially those who live on daily income, to see violence as the only means of surviving or coping during the lockdown (Amusan & Agunyai, 2021).

Psychologist, William James also identified a number of instincts that he believed were essential for survival. These included fear, anger, love, shame and cleanliness. The observations on instinct theory noted that people engage in certain behavior to enhance their survival. Also, he stated that, the instinct theory is essential for survival and it is relevant to the COVID-19 pandemic (Cherry & Swaim, 2020). This is so because people were very afraid of the pandemic. The citizens were angry against the federal, state and local governments for not giving them enough relief materials or palliatives but hoarded some of the items. However, the youths exhibited their grievances during the 'End SARS' crisis by looting stores where the palliatives were kept in all the States in Nigeria, accusing the governments of no distributing the food stuffs meant for the people as a coping strategy (Afolabi & Olatoyo, 2021). While countries and communities have employed different approaches in coping with the pandemic and lockdown, most families have had to employ idiosyncratic approaches in dealing with their peculiar challenges. At this level, the coping strategies have been influenced by characteristics such as gender, pre-existing health conditions, type of employment, and other socio-demographic factors (Adom et al., 2020; Asmundson et al., 2020; Venuleo et al., 2020). Earlier studies also suggest that the utility of coping strategies are context-specific (Aldwin, 2009; Park et al., 2020). Understanding which coping mechanism work in a given setting is therefore critical for the planning of interventions and public health policy in crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Iddi et al., 2021).

Family is defined as a unit of two or more persons united by marriage, blood, adoption, or consensual union, in general consulting a single household, interacting and communicating with each other (Sharma, 2013). In the absence of adequate social protection or social insurance, most households facing income shocks adopted different coping strategies to maintain survival. Carver (2013) defines coping as "efforts to prevent or diminish threat, harm, and loss, or to reduce the distress that is often associated with those experiences." Thus, coping is "basic process integral to adaptation and survival, as it depicts how people detect, appraise, deal with, and learn from stressful encounters" (Skinner & Zimmer-Gembeck, 2016). Coping involves use of different strategies and techniques in order to manage the situation. Coping is "problem-focused" when "directed at reducing the threats and losses of the illness," and it is "emotion- focused" when "directed as reducing the negative emotional consequences" (Baloch et al., 2021). The individual attempts to change the source of stress or

redefine the hazardous situation through acceptance, resignation, or other things.

Coping strategies on the other hand is define “as efforts to regulate emotions, behaviors, cognitions, psychophysiology, and environmental aspects in response to the stress of everyday events” (Morales - Rodríguez & Pérez - Mármol, 2019). Coping strategies include, for instance, reducing certain types of consumption, selling productive assets, or borrowing at high interest rates; which can have severe adverse long-term effects on family’s wellbeing (Koos et al., 2020).The pandemic also demanded cleanliness of the family and her members for them to survive. They were expected to wash their hands and faces regularly after returning from necessary outings during the lockdown. Cleanliness helped them to avoid being infected by the virus (Afolabi & Olatoyo, 2021). In the study conducted by Iddi et al. (2021), they found that the level in strategies applied in coping by families depended on their level of education. Many coping strategies such as reading, talking to relatives/friends; physical exercise; following a healthy/balanced diet; drinking water to hydrate; following the news; other social media engagements; pursuing hobbies, listening to music, yoga, or gardening; relaxing or doing home chores have been reported to be helpful during crises among families (Fullana et al., 2020; Jimenez-Pavon et al., 2020; Shama et al., 2020).

However, according to Afolabi and Olatoyo (2021), many Nigerian families had reduced consumption to only a meal per day as a coping strategy. As a result of the lockdown, people in private employment were unable to do their usual business and could not even feed their families. Many of them had to rely on government’s food relief to survive until the lockdown was lifted, which allowed them to embark on some economic and financial activities to enhance their families’ livelihood. Specifically, in Ekiti State, Nigeria, the government in partnership with well-meaning citizens of the State and top government officials launched a rapid response of helping people out with cash, essential commodities like raw and packaged food items to meet their immediate needs during the total lockdown (Afolabi, 2021).During the lean periods between harvests, family coping strategies like remittances from livestock and money lenders allowed people to cope with their needs, including access to food. The most common coping strategies that families used were personal savings, reduced food consumption and other sales (Gash & Gray, 2016). Thus, the scope of the COVID-19 pandemic placed these strategies under severe strain. The harsh effect of COVID-19 pandemic called for immediate actions in order to limit more risks and struggling of households and their livelihoods either in rural and urban areas in Nigeria. People had to depend on targeted food distribution, cash transfer and other social supports, seedlings and farming extension services from federal, state governments and philanthropists countrywide. This was what sustained the populace including families in Nsukka urban during the total lockdown until the gradual relaxation of it (Afolabi & Olatoyo, 2021). Nsukka is a town and a local Government Area in Enugu State, Nigeria. It is the most populated amongst the seventeen Local Government Areas in Enugu State according to population Statistics. It shares a border with Edem, Opi, Ede-Oballa, and Obimo. Its population projection according to National Beaura of Statistics (2016) is 417,700. Nsukka urban is made up of three communities which are Nkpunano, Nru, and Ihe-Owerre.

1.1. Statement of Problem

This study was conceived out of the concern of people and families on the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic, which affected all nations of the world and led to total lockdown of businesses and offices. Unfortunately, this outbreak of the virus and its spread to countries including Nigeria has had a destructive impact on health, economy, infrastructures, human existence and food. However, recent studies and literature showed that more researchers, governments, and major stakeholders have rather engaged in research that intends to bring a cure to the virus (Amusan & Agunyai, 2021). It is in view of this that the research was conducted to find out the coping strategies families adopted during lockdown in order to survive.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The broad objectives of this study are to determine the coping strategies adopted by Nigerian families during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- (a) Determine the types of businesses families engaged in during COVID-19 lockdown.
- (b) Ascertain the gifts gotten by families that helped them during COVID-19 lockdown.
- (c) Determine the safety measures adopted by families, which helped them to overcome COVID-19 pandemic.

1.3. Research Questions

Based on the research objectives in line with the topic of this research, the following research questions were raised as follows:

- (a) What are the types of businesses your family engaged in from home during COVID-19 lockdown?
- (b) What are the sources of gifts that helped families during COVID-19 lockdown?
- (c) What are the safety measures observed by families that helped them not to contract COVID-19 pandemic?

1.4. Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the families that did businesses from home during COVID-19 and those that did not do.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of families that received gifts during COVID-19 lockdown and those who did not receive.

H₀₃: There is a significant difference between families who observed safety measures and those who did not during COVID-19 lockdown.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The design adopted in this study was descriptive survey.

2.2. Ethics Statement

The research was approved by the reviewers committee of Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education in University of Nigeria Nsukka.

2.3. Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Nsukka urban of Enugu state, which covered three communities in Nsukka. They are Nkpunano, Nru and Ihe-Owerre. Nsukka is surrounded by enormous and large farm lands, markets of different sizes, financial institutions, hospitals, police stations, schools of all types and dwellers from all parts of the country and beyond with different ethnic, religious and socio-cultural background; this gave Nsukka urban the opportunity of having great number of families and also the choice of this study.

2.4. Population and Sample

Population of study comprised of 417,700 families from the three communities in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu state. A sample size of 399 families (133 from each of the three communities) was drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique with the aid of Taro Yamane's formula. A 4-point rating scale questionnaire which was validated by some experts was used. Test-retest method was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument and data collected were analyzed with Cronbat Alpha which yielded are liability coefficient of 0.70.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The instrument was administered through direct contact with the respondents and out of the total 399 copies administered, 397 copies were retrieved and used for analysis.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

Data collected relative to the research questions were analyzed with arithmetic mean and standard deviation while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Research question one:* What are the types of businesses family engaged in from home during COVID-19 lockdown?

Table 1: Respondent mean rate of the type of businesses family engaged in from home during COVID-19 lockdown in Nsukka Urban (n=397)

S/N	Types of businesses family engaged in from home during COVID-19 lockdown	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1.	Home gardening	2.47	1.25	M
2.	Making of local nose mask	3.94	1.26	VH
3.	Making of hand sanitizers	3.50	1.26	VH
4.	Home baking	3.33	1.31	H
5.	Door to door supply of food	1.44	1.30	L
6.	Poultry farming	3.74	1.77	VH
7.	Sewing clothes for people	1.44	1.30	L
8.	Learning of skills online	2.47	1.25	M
9.	Soap, cream and detergent production	2.18	1.01	M
	Grand mean	2.72	1.30	M

Key for Interpretation

\bar{x} , 0.00 – 1.49 = Low (L)

\bar{x} , 1.50 – 2.49 = Moderate (M)

\bar{x} , 2.50 – 3.49 = High (H)

\bar{x} , 3.50 – 4.00 = Very high (VH)

Data in Table 1 showed that overall, family's engagement to businesses during COVID-19 lockdown was moderate ($\bar{x} = 2.72$, $SD = 1.30$). The result also shows that most of the families were into making of local nose mask ($\bar{x} = 3.94$, $SD = 1.26$), poultry farming ($\bar{x} = 3.74$, $SD = 1.77$) and making of hand sanitizers ($\bar{x} = 3.50$, $SD = 1.26$). The Table further revealed that families were also into Home baking ($\bar{x} = 3.33$, $SD = 1.31$), home gardening and learning of skills online ($\bar{x} = 2.47$, $SD = 1.25$), soap, cream and detergent production ($\bar{x} = 2.18$, $SD = 1.01$), door to door supply of food and sewing clothes for people ($\bar{x} = 2.18$, $SD = 1.01$). This implies that families' engagement to business during COVID-19 lockdown in Nsukka urban was generally moderate.

3.2. *Research question two:* What are the sources of gifts that helped families during COVID-19 lockdown?

Table 2: Mean rate of the sources of gifts that helped families during COVID-19 lockdown in Nsukka Metropolis (n=397)

S/N	Sources of gifts that helped families during COVID-19 lockdown in Nsukka Urban	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1.	Government palliatives	1.44	1.30	L
2.	Gifts from relatives and friends	3.50	1.26	VH
3.	Gifts from non-governmental organizations	2.15	1.25	M
4.	Gifts from philanthropists	2.15	1.25	M
5.	Money from saved family income	3.94	1.26	VH
6.	Bank loans / overdrafts	3.50	1.26	VH
7.	Gifts from churches	3.94	1.26	VH
	Grand mean	2.95	1.26	H

Key for Interpretation

\bar{x} , 0.00 – 1.49 = Low (L)

\bar{x} , 1.50 – 2.49 = Moderate (M)

\bar{x} , 2.50 – 3.49 = High (H)

\bar{x} , 3.50 – 4.00 = Very high (VH)

Data in Table 2 showed that overall, the rate at which families received gifts during the COVID-19 lockdown was high ($\bar{x} = 2.95$, $SD = 1.26$). The result shows that most of the families were using money from saved family income and they received gifts from churches ($\bar{x} = 3.94$, $SD = 1.26$), gifts from relatives and friends and also bank loans / overdrafts ($\bar{x} = 3.50$, $SD = 1.26$), gifts from non-governmental organizations and philanthropists ($\bar{x} = 2.15$, $SD = 1.25$), government palliatives ($\bar{x} = 1.44$, $SD = 1.30$). This implies that the families' sources of gifts in Nsukka urban during COVID-19 lockdown were high.

3.3. *Research question three:* What are the safety measures observed by families that helped them not to contract COVID-19 pandemic?

Table 3: Respondent mean rate of the safety measures observed by families that helped them not to contract COVID-19 pandemic in Nsukka urban (n=397)

S/N	Safety measures observed by families that helped them not to contract COVID-19 pandemic in Nsukka urban	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1.	Washing hands regularly with soap and water	3.94	1.26	VH
2.	Cleaning of hands with hand sanitizer	3.94	1.26	VH
3.	Avoiding a large gathering	3.78	1.31	VH
4.	Covering ones nose with mask	3.94	1.26	VH
5.	Sneezing into your elbow or a tissue paper	3.30	1.39	H
6.	Reporting cases that are related to COVID-19 symptoms to hospitals and other related organizations	2.50	1.35	H
7.	Visiting hospital for proper check-up when sick	2.50	1.35	H
8.	Shaking hands with elbow	1.96	1.44	M
9.	Wearing hand gloves	1.96	1.44	M
	Grand mean	3.09	1.34	H

Key for Interpretation

\bar{x} , 0.00 – 1.49 = Low (L)

\bar{x} , 1.50 – 2.49 = Moderate (M)

\bar{x} , 2.50 – 3.49 = High (H)

\bar{x} , 3.50 – 4.00 = Very high (VH)

Data in Table 3 showed that overall, the rate of safety measures observed by families that helped them not to contract COVID-19 during the pandemic was high ($\bar{x} = 3.09$, $SD = 1.34$). The result revealed that families wash their hands regularly with soap and water, clean their hands with hand sanitizer and always cover their nose with mask ($\bar{x} = 3.94$, $SD = 1.26$), they also avoid large gathering ($\bar{x} = 3.78$, $SD = 1.31$), families also sneeze into their elbow or using a tissue paper ($\bar{x} = 3.30$, $SD = 1.39$). The Table further shows that families report cases that are related to COVID-19 symptoms to hospitals and other related organizations, they also visit hospital for proper check-up when sick ($\bar{x} = 2.50$, $SD = 1.35$), families in Nsukka urban shake hands with elbow and also wear hand gloves as a safety measure against COVID-19 pandemic ($\bar{x} = 1.96$, $SD = 1.44$). This implies that families’ in Nsukka urban observed some safety measures that helped them not to contract COVID-19 pandemic during the lockdown.

3.4. Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference between the families that did business from home during COVID-19 and those that did not.

Table 4: Summary of z-test analysis of the mean ratings of respondents that did business from home during COVID-19 and those that did not do.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	A	df	z-cal	z-crit	Remark
Families that did business	200	4.26	0.41	0.05	226	1.69	1.96	Not Rejected
Families that did not do business	197	4.35	0.37					

Data in Table 4 show that the calculated z-value of 1.69 at 226 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance is less than the z-table value of 1.96. This means that there is no significance difference between the mean ratings of respondents that did business and those that did not do business in Nsukka Urban during the COVID-19 lockdown. Hence, the hypothesis was not rejected.

3.5. Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of families that received gifts during COVID-19 lockdown and those who did not receive.

Table 5: Summary of z-test analysis of the mean ratings of respondents that received gifts during COVID-19 lockdown and those who did not receive.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	A	df	z-cal	z-crit	
Remark								
Families that received gifts	200	4.33	0.44					
				0.05	226	1.83	1.96	Not
Rejected								
Families that did not receive gifts	197	4.43	0.40					

Data in Table 5 show that the calculated z-value of 1.83 at 226 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance is less than the z-table value of 1.96. This means that there is no significance difference between the mean ratings of respondents that received gifts during COVID-19 lockdown and those who did not receive. Hence, the hypothesis was not rejected.

3.6. Hypothesis three: There is a significant difference between families who observed safety measures and those who did not during COVID-19 lockdown.

Table 6: Summary of z-test analysis of the ratings of respondents that observed safety measures and those who did not during COVID-19 lockdown.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	A	df	z-cal	z-crit	
Remark								
Families that observed safety measures	200	4.30	0.50					
				0.05	226	0.31	1.96	Not
Rejected								
Families that did not observe	197	4.28	0.63					

Data in Table 6 show that the calculated z-value of 0.31 at 226 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance is less than the z-table value of 1.96. This means that there is a significance difference between the mean ratings of respondents that observed safety and those who did not observed safety measures during COVID-19 lockdown. Hence, the hypothesis was not rejected.

Nevertheless, these results must be interpreted with caution and a number of limitations should be borne in mind. Some of the families dishonored the questionnaire due to disturbance in continuation of their duties. Efforts had to be put in, in explaining and persuading them to respond to the questionnaire stressing that it is for study. In the scope of discussion, all the parts in Nsukka LGA could have been studied but the researchers was unable to do that. Therefore, there is need for further studies. Such limitations like time and money were encountered as limitations. The researchers found this challenging especially while collecting data from the respondents in various parts of Nsukka urban. Time is another problem as journal research has deadline for submission. Therefore, researchers suggest adequate time to be given to this kind of study for proper result findings. Finally, the researchers also suggest more studies on this topic to examine the consequences of COVID-19 pandemic lockdown in lifestyle of families in Nsukka urban of Enugu state.

4. Conclusion

While many studies have explored the effects of the pandemic to the society in general, limited studies focused on the coping strategies adopted by families during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown, particularly those in Nsukka urban. This study examined the coping strategies adopted by families during COVID-19 pandemic lockdown in Nsukka urban of Enugu state. Based on the study, it was observed that most of the families in Nsukka urban were into making of local nose mask during the COVID-19 lockdown. However, families were also using money from saved family income as a means of survival during this period. This study further revealed that the families most observed safety measure during COVID-19 lockdown is regular washing of hands with soap and water and cleaning of hands with hand sanitizer; they cover their nose with mask. The following recommendations are made: available media platforms should be actively engaged by the Federal government to ensure that family members and the community at large are equipped with good health literacy. There is need for federal government to promote, support and embed psychological support initiatives in work place, and provide occupational or financial support to families prevented from or not working.

Acknowledgements

The researchers would like to acknowledge and reserve a memory lane for Professor N. M. Eze and Professor C. A. Igbo for all their support throughout our academic career. We also wish to acknowledge the role of our reviewers and their editorial director for their suggestion and thorough editing as well as their patience in working with us. Finally, as the corresponding author, I wish to appreciate the effort of my husband; Mr. S. O. Ezuwgu, my children and my friends; Mr. L. C. Ali and Mrs. N. J. Ali.

Conflict of Interest

The authors hereby state that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, methodology, draft writing, review writing, data collection and analysis were carried out by the 1st author. However, validation, supervision, review and editing of the manuscript were carried out by the 2nd author.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Funding Information

The authors have no funding to disclose.

References

- Adom, D, Adu-Mensah, J., & Sekyere, P. A. (2020). Hand-to-mouth work culture and the COVID-19 lockdown restrictions: experiences of selected informal sector workers in Kumasi, Ghana. *Research Journal in Advanced Humanities*, 1, 45–63.
- Afolabi, C. Y., & Olatayo, S. A. (2021). COVID-19 Pandemic, Livelihood and Coping Strategies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Health and Psychology Research*, 9, 45-70.
- Ajide, K. B., Ibrahim, R. L., & Alimi, O. Y. (2020). Estimating the impacts of lockdown on COVID-19 cases in Nigeria. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 7, 100217. DOI: 10.1016/j.trip.2020.100217
- Aldwin, C. M. (2009). *Stress, coping, and development: An Integrative Perspective*. Guilford press.
- Amusan, L., & Agunyai, S. C. (2021). The COVID-19 pandemic and the crisis of lockdowns in Nigeria: The household food security perspective. *Africa's Public Service Delivery & Performance Review*, 9, 10. <https://doi.org/10.4102/apsdpr.v9i1.484>
- Asmundson, G. J., Paluszek, M. M., Landry, C. A., Rachor, G. S., McKay, D. & Taylor, S. (2020). Do pre-existing anxiety related and mood disorders differentially impact COVID-19 stress responses and coping? *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 74, 102271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102271>
- Baloch, G. M., Kamaludin, K., Chinna, K., Sundarasan, S., Nurunnabi, M., Khoshaim, H. B., Hossain, S. F. A., Al-Sukayt, A., & Baloch, L. G. (2021). Coping with COVID-19: The strategies adapted by Pakistani students to overcome implications. *International Journal of Environmental Research in Public Health*, 18, 17-99. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18041799>
- Berger, Z. D., Nicholas, G. E., Alexandra, L. P. & Ross, D. S. (2020). Covid-19: Control measures must be equitable and inclusive, *British Medical Journal*, 368. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1141>
- Cai, J., Sun, W., Huang, J., Gamber, M., Wu, J., & He, G. (2020). Indirect virus transmission in cluster of COVID-19 cases, Wenzhou, China, 2020. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 26, 1343. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2606.200412>
- Carver, C.M., Reddy, D.S. Neurosteroid (2013) Interactions with synaptic and extrasynaptic GABAA receptors: regulation of subunit plasticity, phasic and tonic inhibition, and

- neuronal network excitability. *Psychopharmacology*, 230, 151–188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00213-013-3276-5>
- Centers for Disease Control - CDC. (2020). Coronavirus (COVID-19). Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/index.html> (accessed July 14, 2022).
- Cherry, K. & Swaim, E. (2020). How the instinct theory explains motivation. Retrieved from <https://www.vertwellmind.com/kendra-cherry-2794702/emily-swaim-4798013>. (accessed July 14, 2022).
- Ehanire, D. (2020). Nigeria Centre for Disease Control. Retrieved from <https://ncdc.gov.ng/news/227/first-case-of-corona-virus-disease-confirmed-in-nigeria> (accessed July 14, 2022).
- Fontanesi, L., Marchetti, D., Mazza, C., Di Giandomenico, S., Roma, P. & Verrocchio, M. C. (2020). The effect of the COVID-19 lockdown on parents: A Call to adopt urgent measures. *Psychological Trauma: Theory, Research, Practice, and Policy*, 12(1), 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.1037/tra0000672>.
- Gash, M., & Gray, B. (2016). The role of financial services in building household resilience in Burkina Faso. CGAP Clients at the Center.
- Kelly, H. (2011). The classical definition of a pandemic is not elusive. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 89, 540-541.
- Iddi, S., Obiri-Yeboah, D., Aboh, I. K., Quansah, R., Owusu, S. A., Enyan, N. I. E., & Armah, F. A. (2021). Coping strategies adapted by Ghanaians during the COVID-19 crisis and lockdown: A population-based study. *Plosone*, 16, e0253800. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0253800>
- Koos, C., Hangoma, P., & Mæstad, O. (2020). Household wellbeing and coping strategies in Africa during COVID-19—findings from high frequency phone surveys. Chr. Michelsen Institute.
- Lattouf, A. (2020). Domestic violence spikes during coronavirus as families trapped at home. Retrieved from <https://10daily.com.au/news/australia/a200326zyjkh/domestic-violence-spikes-uringcoronavirus-as-families-trapped-at-home-20200327> (accessed July 14, 2022).
- Liu, J. J., Bao, Y., Huang, X., Shi, J., & Lu, L. (2020). Mental health considerations for children quarantined because of COVID-19. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*, 4(5), 347-349. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642\(20\)30096-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642(20)30096-1).
- Morales-Rodríguez, F. M., & Pérez-Mármol, J. M. (2019). The role of anxiety, coping strategies, and emotional intelligence on general perceived self-efficacy in university students. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 1689. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01689>
- Nigeria Centre for Disease Control -NCDC (2020). Confirmed COVID-19 cases by state. Retrieved from <https://covid19.ncdc.gov.ng/> (accessed July 14, 2022).
- Obiakor, T., Iheonu, C. & Ihezue, E. (2021). *COVID-19 in Nigeria*. Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa.
- Oke, O. (2020). The impact on Nigeria of the coronavirus pandemic: Socioeconomic pandemonium. Retrieved from <https://www.marxist.com/the-impact-on-nigeria-of-the-coronavirus-pandemic-socioeconomic-pandemonium.html> (accessed July 14, 2022).

- Park, C. L., Russell, B. S., Fendrich, M., Finkelstein-Fox, L., Hutchison, M., & Becker, J. (2020). Americans' COVID-19 stress, coping, and adherence to CDC guidelines. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 35, 2296–2303. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-020-05898-9>.
- Peterman, A., Potts, A., O'Donnell, M., Thompson, K., Shah, N., Oertelt-Prigione, S., & Van Gelder, N. (2020). *Pandemics and violence against women and children*, 528. Washington, DC: Center for Global Development.
- Piguillem, F., & Shi, L. (2022). Optimal COVID-19 quarantine and testing policies. *The Economic Journal*, 132, 2534-2562.
- Sharma, R. (2013). The family and family structure classification redefined for the current times. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 2, 306.
- Skinner, E. A., & Zimmer-Gembeck, M. J. (2016). Development of coping during adolescence: Heightened reactivity, pro-active regulation, and increased coping flexibility. In *The Development of Coping*, 185-209. Springer, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20590776.2022.2109959>
- Someshwar, H., Sarvaiya, P., Desai, S., Gogri, P., Someshwar, J., Mehendale, P., & Bhatt, G. (2020). Does social distancing during the lock down due to COVID-19 outbreak in Mumbai affect quality of life? *International Journal of Clinical and Biomedical Research*, 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.31878/ijcbr.2020.62.01>
- Spinelli, M., Lionetti, F., Pastore, M. & Fasolo, M. (2020). Parents' stress and children's psychological problems in families facing the COVID-19 outbreak in Italy. *Frontiers Psychology*, 11, 1713. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01713>.
- Sprang, G., & Silman, M. (2013). Posttraumatic stress disorder in parents and youth after health-related disasters. *Disaster Medical and Public Health Preparedness*, 7, 105–110.
- Stiglitz, J. (2002). *Globalization and its discontents*. Penguin Books.
- United Nations Coordinated Appeal (2020). Global humanitarian response plan COVID-19. A working paper of the Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), Geneva. Retrieved from https://www.un.org/development/desa/ageing/wp-content/uploads/sites/24/2020/05/GHRP-COVID19_May_Update.pdf. (accessed April 20, 2021).
- Venuleo, C., Marinaci, T., Gennaro, A. & Palmieri, A. (2020). The meaning of living in the time of COVID-19. A large sample narrative inquiry. *Frontiers Psychology*, 11, 577077. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.577077>.
- Wang, L., Li, J., Guo, S., Xie, N., Yao, L., Cao, Y., & Sun, D. (2020). Real-time estimation and prediction of mortality caused by COVID-19 with patient information based algorithm. *Science of the Total Environment*, 727, 138394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138394>
- World Health Organization (WHO) (2020). Novel-Coronavirus-2019 Situation Reports. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/situation-reports/> (accessed July 30, 2022).

Publisher: Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka 41001, Nigeria

© 2022 the Author(s), licensee Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)